

COMPATIBILITY OF TRADITIONAL AND INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN EDUCATING PRIMARY STUDENTS IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: This article examines the issue of combining national values and modern technologies in the primary education system in the era of digital transformation. The study analyzes the best practices of countries such as Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Estonia, and Canada, and shows ways to integrate traditional pedagogical heritage with modern digital tools. As a result, practical recommendations for the education system of Uzbekistan are formulated.

Keywords: digital transformation, primary education, national values, innovative pedagogy, international experience, educational technologies, national education, information technologies.

The modern era is characterized by the unprecedented pace of technological development in history. Information and communication technologies have covered almost all aspects of human life, from production to interpersonal relationships. The field of education has not been left out of this process. Today, digital tools are becoming an integral part of the educational process. As a result, the issue of preserving national identity in the context of globalization is more important than ever. Amidst the influx of different cultures and values, it has become an urgent need to convey the rich heritage of one's people to the younger generation. Finding a balance between these two trends - technological modernization and strengthening national identity - is one of the main problems of modern pedagogy.

As the head of our country noted in his Address to the Oliy Majlis of December 29, 2020, the acquisition of digital knowledge and information technologies is of crucial importance in achieving sustainable development [1]. This idea determines the strategic role of technologies in the process of modernization of the education system. At the same time, the concept of “Continuous Spiritual Education”, approved by the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2019, establishes the formation of loyalty to the Motherland, national pride, and spiritual and moral qualities in the younger generation as a priority task [2]. Thus, the parallel development of technological progress and national education is the main direction of modern educational policy.

The purpose of this article is to theoretically substantiate the ways of combining traditional pedagogical approaches and modern technologies in educating primary school students in a digital learning environment, as well as to conduct a comparative analysis of international experience.

In recent decades, the term “digital learning environment” has firmly established itself in the pedagogical lexicon. Different researchers interpret this concept from different perspectives, which indicates its versatility and complexity.

Domestic scientists N. Muslimov and M. Lutfillayev describe electronic educational resources as an interactive space that ensures the interaction of participants in the educational process [5]. In their approach, the communicative function of technology is prioritized. I. Ergashev calls the digital environment an integrated system created using ICT tools [6]. J. Nazirov believes that the main feature of the digital environment is the ability to adapt to the personal needs of users [7].

In foreign literature, this term also has different meanings. American researcher K. Forrest distinguishes between traditional Internet pages and real interactive platforms, which serves as an important methodological basis for designing educational platforms [17]. A. Masrani and his colleagues present the digital environment as a holistic system and propose a model of an electronic ecosystem [21]. South Korean expert Kim Jin Hae emphasizes a broader approach, evaluating the digital environment as a source of not only technical, but also cognitive and even linguistic changes [19].

This issue is also being actively studied in the CIS countries. Russian scientists L.V. Savchenko and A.V. Platonova define the digital educational environment as a set of technological, information and methodological resources necessary to achieve the specified results [24]. Kazakh researcher K. Buzaubakova describes it as a set of open and distributed information systems [15].

Summarizing the above views, the digital educational environment can be defined as follows: a digital educational environment is a pedagogical system organized on the basis of modern information technologies, ensuring effective interaction of all participants in the educational process, free from time and space boundaries, adaptable to individual needs, and its main features include interactivity, the possibility of individualization, the use of multimedia formats, remote collaboration and mobility.

Education is a purposeful pedagogical activity carried out with the aim of preparing the younger generation for social life and forming spiritual and moral qualities in them. Education is a systematic process aimed at comprehensively developing the younger generation based on a specific goal and socio-historical experience [3]. National education is a form of this process based on a specific national culture, traditions and values. All noble goals can be achieved through education and upbringing [4]. This determines the decisive place of upbringing in the development of the younger

generation and shows the inextricable link between the two components of the pedagogical process - education and upbringing.

The problem of national education has been studied by many scientists at different times. M. Aminov defines education as the process of forming the necessary qualities for a person to successfully function in society [8]. M. Galdiyeva emphasizes the joint influence of the family, school and social environment in the development of national consciousness in primary school students [9]. Kh. Jabborov explains national education through spiritual and moral qualities manifested in behavior [10]. R. Mavlonova considers national education to be a form of universal human values adapted to local conditions, that is, a national form of universal human education [11]. M. Qur'anov sees it as a There are similar views in foreign pedagogy. American J. Dewey emphasized the importance of national values in civic education [16]. French sociologist É. Durkheim sees education as a means of ensuring the stability of society [18]. Turkish scientist Ziya Gökalp describes national education as the process of transforming knowledge into the spiritual habits of an individual [18].

Thus, national education is a complex pedagogical process aimed at the comprehensive development of the individual, the formation of his national identity, based on the historical experience, cultural heritage and value system of a particular people.

The introduction of digital technologies into the field of education is somewhat alarming. This is because the virtual environment can alienate children from real life and alienate them from national values. After all, today's children are constantly in contact with content reflecting the cultures of different countries. means of transferring cultural heritage to generations and ensuring national security [13].

Through social networks, video platforms, online games, they are exposed to foreign trends, views and lifestyles. As a result, some children may develop negative attitudes, such as indifference to their national identity and disregard for the heritage of their ancestors. The fact that foreign cartoon characters are becoming more popular among primary school students than characters from national fairy tales is a clear example of this. However, from another perspective, digital tools also allow us to present national values in a new way, making them interesting and understandable for the younger generation. The pedagogical potential of modern technologies is very wide:

Firstly, examples of national oral creativity - fairy tales, legends, epics can be processed in the form of animated films and interactive books. Secondly, the past is brought to life by creating multimedia projects about historical figures and events. Thirdly, through virtual museums and excursions, cultural heritage will be accessible to everyone, regardless of territorial borders. Fourthly, national music and art can be promoted in a modern format - through podcasts, video tutorials, interactive applications.

In general, there is no natural conflict between technology and national education - the main thing is to use digital tools in the right direction, in accordance with pedagogical goals. Technology should not be a means of destroying national values, but a means of conveying them to the new generation in a new language.

Different countries have developed their own approaches to integrating digital education and national values. The study analyzed the experience of five countries - Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Estonia and Canada. These countries were selected based on several criteria: high performance in international education rankings, innovation in the field of digital education, experience in preserving national values and successfully integrating technologies. Japan has been implementing the GIGA School program since 2019. The main goal of this initiative is to provide every student with a personal computer or tablet and guarantee high-speed internet access [26]. As of July 2021, 96.2% of students were provided with digital devices [32].

However, along with technological equipment, the Japanese education system has preserved moral education as a separate subject [14]. In the principle of “digital-national balance” developed by Japanese methodologists, children learn national etiquette while using modern devices. According to the Yarimizu methodology, this process takes place in three stages: first, children understand the usefulness of digital tools for national culture, then they learn to use technology in practice along with national values, and finally they learn to constantly demonstrate their national character in their digital lives [27].

Singapore has a unique experience as a multinational state. The country’s population consists of Chinese, Malay, Indian and other ethnic groups, and there are four official languages. The Singapore Student Learning Space (SLS), created as part of the EdTech Masterplan 2030 strategy, works in English, Chinese, Malay and Tamil [28]. Content is prepared for each language group, taking into account cultural characteristics.

The Character and Citizenship Education program will provide citizenship education in a digital environment [29]. The country’s only teacher training institution, the National Institute of Education (NIE), will ensure that all educators are trained to the same high standards [30]. In 2024, specialized certification courses in artificial intelligence will be mandatory for all teacher candidates [18]. South Korea is a world leader in the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies into education. In June 2023, the “AI Digital Textbook Promotion Plan” was announced [20], and from March 2025, AI textbooks will be used in grades 3-4 in mathematics, English, and computer science [31]. Over three years, \$760 million has been allocated for these purposes.

Digital ethics education is carried out in three areas: compliance with digital laws and regulations, protection of personal data and copyright, and digital self-governance [16]. Using VR technologies, the study of Korean history and culture is organized - students

can virtually visit ancient palaces and historical sites [23]. Estonia is recognized as a country that has achieved high results in conditions of limited resources. The Tiger Leap program, implemented since the 1990s, has made the country a leader in digital education [22]. All digital platforms are developed in Estonian, taking into account the local cultural context.

As part of the “ProgeTiger” project, students create national art pieces using computer programs — traditional patterns, national melodies are processed in a modern format [25]. The Estonian Education Strategy 2021-2035 envisages the development of digital pedagogical methods and the use of digital solutions to personalize education [16].

Canada has successfully implemented a multicultural policy in digital education. In 1971, it was the first in the world to announce an official multicultural policy, and the 1988 Multiculturalism Act takes into account the cultural needs of all ethnic groups [33].

The federal government has allocated \$17.6 million over three years, starting in 2023, through the “Digital Literacy Exchange Program” [18]. The organization “MediaSmarts” implements digital literacy programs in the context of national values, organizes special workshops for teachers [26]. The province of British Columbia has identified six areas of digital literacy: creativity, project management, research skills, critical thinking, digital citizenship, and technical operations [18].

Analyzing the practice of the countries considered above, the following general patterns can be distinguished:

Firstly, successful countries work on the basis of long-term strategies. Japan's GIGA program, Singapore's EdTech Masterplan 2030, Estonia's Tiger Leap - all of them were implemented on the basis of 5-10-year plans. Gradual development was preferred, not sudden, hasty changes.

Secondly, technological modernization does not displace national values, but rather enriches them in a new form. In all the countries considered, national culture is actively promoted in digital format. Technology is used not as a goal, but as a means of national education.

Third, teacher training is a crucial factor. Singapore’s National Institute of Education, Japan’s teacher training programs, Estonia’s special training for educators — all of these show that even the most advanced technologies are ineffective without well-trained teachers.

Fourth, it is important to involve all segments of society. South Korea’s experience in introducing AI textbooks shows that it is necessary to take into account the opinions of parents and educators, and to be ready to revise initial plans.

Fifth, social support systems have been created. In Singapore, subsidies for low-income families, in Canada, special programs for indigenous peoples — these are aimed at eliminating digital inequality.

Based on the study of international experience, the following recommendations can be formulated for our country's education system:

1. Priority should be given to the creation of national digital content. Uzbek folk oral literature - fairy tales, proverbs, epics - should be prepared in multimedia format. Epics such as Alpomish and Goroglu can be brought to children in the form of animated series and interactive books, and holidays such as Navruz and Mehrjon can be shown in a virtual format.

2. It is advisable to enrich the subject of "Education" with digital tools. Based on the experience of Japan, it is necessary to combine moral education with modern technologies. Virtual excursions, interactive exercises, multimedia presentations will significantly increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

3. It is necessary to plan the creation of a multilingual educational platform. A single educational platform similar to the Singapore model, working in Uzbek, Russian, Karakalpak and English, can be developed. This is consistent with the multinational structure of our country.

4. Systematic teacher training programs are necessary. Special courses should be organized to improve the digital competence of teachers. This should include not only technical skills, but also the methodology of teaching national values in digital format.

5. A phased implementation strategy should be used. The experience of Korea shows that an effective approach is to first test the innovation in the form of pilot projects, analyze the results, take into account the opinions of all stakeholders, and then implement it on a large scale.

In conclusion, it can be said that there is no natural conflict between digital technologies and national education - they are complementary, enriching elements. Modern tools do not destroy national values, but allow them to be conveyed to the new generation in a new form.

The experience of developed countries shows that the key to success is a long-term strategy, high-quality training of personnel, ensuring the participation of all segments of society, and a phased approach. Each country has created its own unique model based on its cultural characteristics.

Uzbekistan has its own rich cultural heritage, a developing education system, and the high potential of the younger generation. By critically absorbing international experience and adapting it to local conditions, our country can create its own model in the field of digital education - a model in which modern technologies serve to strengthen our national values.

Most importantly, we should not forget that technology is a means, not a goal. The goal is to educate a generation that loves its homeland, values its national values, has modern competencies, and is ready for global competition. It is through this approach that Uzbekistan will succeed in building a modern digital society while preserving its rich cultural heritage.

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